

Speciation of binary complexes of Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} with maleic acid in acetonitrile medium

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Manuscript received online 14 February 2015, revised 28 April 2015, accepted 01 May 2015

Abstract : The stability constants of maleic acid with Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} metal ions in different percentage of acetonitrile-water mixtures having varying dielectric constants have been determined pH metrically. The ionic strength ($m = 0.16 \text{ mol L}^{-1}$) was maintained constant. The stability constants ($\log \beta$) of binary systems found to increase with increase in percentage of acetonitrile. The studies of effect of dielectric constants of medium on the stability constants of Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} metal ion have also been studied. Chemical speciation was discussed based on the distribution diagrams.

Keywords : Chemical speciation, maleic acid, acetonitrile, stability constants.

Introduction

Speciation analysis, the determination of the concentrations of separate and unique atomic and molecular forms of an element instead of its total concentration in a sample is important in human biology, nutrition, toxicology and in clinical practice. However, concentrations of essential, endogenous elements are frequently controlled homeostatically, and instances of pathology arising from altered speciation of these elements are relatively rare. When a major ligand is deficient it is the total concentration, rather than its distribution among species, that is of most diagnostic significance. On the other hand, speciation profoundly influences both the toxicity and bioavailability of an element.

The speciation study of toxic metal ion complexes is useful to understand the role played by the active site cavities in biological molecules and the bonding behavior of protein residues with the metal ion. The species refined and their relative concentrations under the experimental conditions represent the possible forms of maleic acid.

Lead is toxic even at low concentrations for living organisms, who can absorb it in various ways¹. Lead intake by humans can be due to the consumption of crop plants grown on soils with high plant-available metal con-

centrations². It can, however, migrate through the soil with dissolved organic matter³ or mobilized by certain plants⁴. Due to its numerous uses and high persistence, lead is a major environmental contaminant⁵.

Cadmium affects many different kinds of organisms, ranging from microbes to humans. Human exposure to cadmium mainly occurs through cigarette smoking, but exposure can also occur through contaminated food, water, or air⁶. Cadmium is a known carcinogen to mammals⁷. Cadmium can also enter the environment through natural causes, such as volcanic activity and forest fires⁸.

Acetonitrile (AN) is a weak base⁹ and a much weaker acid¹⁰ than water. Therefore cations and especially anions have lower solvation energies in acetonitrile than in water, except in those cases where there is specific interaction with the solvent, thus cations are reduced at considerably more positive¹¹ potential in acetonitrile than in water. It is a protophobic dipolar aprotic solvent and it does not form any hydrogen bond with solute species. The formation of dimers which are shown to exist from IR studies.

Maleic acid is the *cis* isomer of butenedioic acid, whereas fumaric acid is the *trans* isomer. It is a dicarboxylic acid. Maleic acid is a less stable molecule than fumaric acid. The difference in heat of combustion is 22.7 kJ

mol⁻¹. Maleic acid is more soluble in water than fumaric acid. The melting point of maleic acid (135 °C) is also much lower than that of fumaric acid (287 °C). Both properties of maleic acid can be explained on account of the intramolecular hydrogen bonding¹². It is soluble in water and moderately toxic. Inhalation causes irritating of nose and throat. Contact with eyes or skin causes irritation. It is used to make other chemicals and for dyeing and finishing naturally occurring fibers. In industry, maleic acid is derived by hydrolysis of maleic anhydride, the latter being produced by oxidation of benzene or butane¹³. However, conversion of the *cis* isomer into the *trans* isomer is possible by photolysis in the presence of a small amount of bromine¹⁴. Speciation of binary complexes of Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} with maleic acid were reported in micellar media¹⁵⁻¹⁷. Based on the importance of maleic acid (MA) and its involvement in various physiological and chemical reactions, speciation studies of MA with Cd^{II} and Pb^{II} have been undertaken in AN medium.

Experimental

Materials :

Maleic acid (Qualigens, India) solution (0.05 mol L⁻¹) was prepared in triple-distilled deionised water by maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ nitric acid concentration to increase the solubility. Acetonitrile (Merck, India) was used as received. 2 mol L⁻¹ sodium nitrate (Qualigens, India) was prepared to maintain the ionic strength in the titrand. 0.05 mol L⁻¹ aqueous solutions of Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} nitrates were prepared by dissolving G.R. grade (E. Merck, Germany) salts in triple-distilled water maintaining 0.05 mol L⁻¹ nitric acid to suppress the hydrolysis of metal salts. All the solutions were standardized by standard methods. To assess the errors that might have crept into the determination of the concentrations, the data were subjected to analysis of variance of one way classification¹⁸. The strengths of alkali and mineral acid were determined using the Gran plot method^{19,20}.

Apparatus :

The titrimetric data were obtained using ELICO (Model LI-120) pH meter (readability 0.01), which was calibrated with 0.05 mol L⁻¹ potassium hydrogen phthalate in acidic region and 0.01 mol L⁻¹ borax solution in basic region. The glass electrode was equilibrated in a well stirred AN-water mixture containing the inert electrolyte. All the

titrations were carried out in the medium containing varying concentrations of AN-water mixture (0-50% v/v) by maintaining an ionic strength of 0.16 mol L⁻¹ with sodium nitrate at 303.0 ± 0.1 K. The effect of variation in asymmetry potential, liquid junction potential, activity coefficient, sodium ion error, and dissolved carbon dioxide on the response of glass electrode was accounted for in the form of correction factor^{21,22}.

Procedure :

For the determination of stability constants of metal-ligand binary species, initially titrations of strong acid with alkali were carried out at regular intervals to check whether complete equilibration was achieved. Then the calomel electrode was refilled with AN-water mixture of equivalent composition as that of titrand. In each of the titrations, the titrand consisted of approximately 1 mmol mineral acid in a total volume of 50 ml. Titrations with different ratios 1 : 2.5, 1 : 3.75 and 1 : 5.0 in the case of Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} of metal-to-ligand were carried out with 0.4 mol L⁻¹ sodium hydroxide. Other experimental details are given elsewhere²³.

Modelling strategy :

The computer program SCPHD²⁴ was used to calculate the correction factor. The binary stability constants were calculated with the pH-metric titration data using the computer program MINIQAD75²⁵, which exploits the advantage of a constrained least-squares method in the initial refinement and reliable convergence of the Marquardt algorithm. During the refinement of the binary systems, the correction factor and the protonation constants of maleic acid were fixed. The variation of stability constants with the dielectric constants of the medium was analysed on electrostatic grounds based on solute-solute and solute-solvent interactions.

Results and discussion

The results of the best-fit models that contain the stoichiometry of the complex species and their overall formation constants along with some of the important statistical parameters are given in Table 1. A very low standard deviation in log β values indicates the precision of these parameters. The small values of U_{corr} (the sum of squares of deviations in concentrations of reactants at all experimental points) corrected for degrees of freedom, indicate that the model can represent the experimental

data. Small values of mean, standard deviation and mean deviation for the systems corroborate that the residuals are around a zero mean with little dispersion. Kurtosis is a measure of the peakedness of the error distribution near a model value. For an ideal normal distribution Kurtosis value should be three (mesokurtic)^{26,27}. If the Kurtosis is less than three, the peak of the error distribution curve is flat (platykurtic) and if the Kurtosis is greater than three, the distribution shall have sharp peak (leptokurtic). The Kurtosis values in the present study indicate that the residuals form leptokurtic as well as platykurtic patterns and very few form mesokurtic patterns. The values of Skewness recorded in Table are between 0.04 and 4.34. These data suggest that the residuals form a part of normal distribution. Hence, least-squares method can be applied to the present data. The sufficiency of the model is further evident from the low crystallographic *R*-values. These statistical parameters thus show that the best fit models portray the metal-ligand species in AN media.

alkali, mineral acid, ligand and metal (Table 2). The order of the reactants that influence the magnitudes of stability constants due to incorporation of errors is alkali > acid > ligand > metal. Some species were even rejected when errors are introduced in the concentrations. The rejection of some species and increased standard deviations in the stability constants on introduction of errors confirm the suitability of the experimental conditions (concentrations of reactants) and choice of the best fit models.

Effect of solvent :

The variation of protonation constant or change in free energy with co-solvent content depends upon two factors, viz. electrostatic and non-electrostatic. Born's classical treatment holds good in accounting for the electrostatic contribution to the free energy change²⁸. According to this treatment, the energy of electrostatic interaction is related to dielectric constant. Hence, the logarithm of overall stability constant (log β) should vary linearly as a function of the reciprocal of the dielectric

Table 1. Parameters of best fit chemical models of M(II)-maleic acid complexes in AN-water medium

% v/v	log β _{mlh} (SD)			NP	U _{corr}	Skewness	χ ²	R-Factor	Kurtosis	pH-range
	ML ₂	ML ₃	ML ₂ H							
	Pb ^{II}									
0	7.90(19)	10.73(15)	13.38(05)	75	4.82	0.04	12.62	0.0166	2.35	2.0-6.0
10	8.03(61)	11.42(28)	14.07(13)	69	26.08	0.28	9.77	0.0412	5.06	2.0-6.5
20	8.13(22)	10.97(27)	14.10(06)	65	3.61	0.29	13.78	0.0133	3.96	2.0-6.0
30	8.77(92)	13.02(29)	15.10(11)	13	7.32	0.33	6.33	0.0151	3.73	3.0-6.0
40	8.46(45)	12.11(61)	14.35(12)	9	3.13	0.32	5.89	0.0158	4.20	3.0-6.0
50	9.17(92)	13.49(86)	15.26(09)	15	2.08	0.15	4.24	0.0136	4.15	2.9-6.0
	Cd ^{II}									
0	6.91(79)	12.52(61)	9.57(09)	41	87.08	3.36	114.33	0.1086	13.37	3.0-8.5
10	7.22(74)	13.80(15)	10.49(28)	75	46.57	3.71	74.21	0.0557	22.45	2.0-8.0
20	8.12(30)	14.52(14)	10.46(45)	75	29.09	1.95	32.10	0.0437	10.14	2.0-8.0
30	8.07(69)	15.15(14)	11.74(24)	83	25.30	4.34	182.26	0.0383	26.70	2.0-8.0
40	8.80(24)	16.35(15)	11.32(54)	58	125.09	0.73	36.85	0.1013	6.82	2.0-8.0
50	9.87(55)	16.57(46)	12.05(69)	33	18.36	2.98	32.96	0.0479	13.12	3.0-8.0

U_{corr} = U/(NP - m) × 10⁸, where m = number of species; NP = number of experimental points; SD = standard deviation.

Effect of systematic errors on best fit model :

In order to obtain the best chemical model for critical evaluation and application under varied experimental conditions with different accuracies of data acquisition, an investigation was undertaken by introducing pessimistic errors in the influential parameters like concentrations of

constant (1/*D*) of the medium. These plots (Fig. 1) in AN-water mixtures show that the log β values are linearly increasing with decreasing dielectric constant values.

Distribution diagrams :

Maleic acid is a bidentate ligand that has two dissociable (carboxyl groups) protons. The different forms of maleic

Table 2. Effect of errors in influential parameters on the stability constants of Cd^{II}-maleic acid complexes in 10% v/v AN-water medium

Ingredient	% Error	log β _{mlh} (SD)		
		120	130	121
Acid	0	7.22(74)	10.48(28)	13.80(15)
	-5	Rejected	13.38(38)	15.50(32)
	-2	8.22(67)	11.58(31)	14.49(19)
	+2	7.24(26)	Rejected	13.24(20)
	+5	Rejected	5.35(**)	Rejected
Alkali	-5	Rejected	Rejected	Rejected
	-2	Rejected	5.05(**)	Rejected
	+2	Rejected	12.17(41)	14.63(29)
	+5	Rejected	15.52(**)	16.21(86)
	Ligand	-5	7.73(**)	11.60(33)
	-2	7.74(**)	10.94(35)	14.01(19)
	+2	Rejected	Rejected	Rejected
	+5	6.88(23)	Rejected	13.12(18)
Metal	-5	7.18(98)	10.61(26)	13.89(15)
	-2	7.20(**)	10.52(33)	13.83(18)
	+2	7.22((86)	10.45(34)	13.78(17)
	+5	7.21(61)	10.37(28)	13.73(15)

Fig. 1. Variation of overall stability constant values of metal-maleic acid complexes with AN-water mixtures : (A) Pb^{II} and (B) Cd^{II}; (■) log β_{ML₂}; (▲) log β_{ML₃} and (●) log β_{ML₂H}.

acid are LH₂, LH⁻ and L²⁻ in the pH range 1.5–3.5, 3.5–8.0 and 4.0–8.0, respectively. Hence, the plausible binary metal-ligand complexes can be predicted from these data. The present investigation reveals the existence of ML₂H, ML₂ and ML₃ for Pb^{II} and Cd^{II}. The ML₂ species is the predominant species (Fig. 2) at higher pH and ML₂H is the predominant species at lower pH among all the binary complexes. Low concentration of free metal ion (FM) indicates the strong complexing nature of maleic acid. The formation of various binary complex spe-

Fig. 2. Distribution diagrams of maleic acid complexes in 20% v/v AN-water medium : (A) Pb^{II} and (B) Cd^{II}.

cies is shown in the following equilibria. Some typical distribution diagrams of AN-water media are shown in Fig. 2. The species of ML₂H, ML₃ and ML₂ are formed in the pH range of 1.5–7.0 for Pb^{II} and 1.5–10.0 for Cd^{II} respectively. ML₂H is formed at lower pH and ML₂, ML₃ are formed with the increasing pH. ML₃ and ML₂ species percentage successively increases with increasing pH. Successive deprotonation of ML₂H₂, MLH and protonation of ML forms ML₂H [Equilibria (1), (2) and (3)]. ML₂ formed at higher pH [Equilibria (5), (6) and (7)]. The percentage of the ML₂ species increases successively

Fig. 3. Structures of binary complexes of maleic acid with M(II). Where S is either solvent or water molecule.

with increase in pH. The concentration of ML₂H species decreased, while the concentration of ML₂ and ML₃ increased in the pH range.

Structures of complexes :

Depending upon the nature of the ligands and the metal ions and based on the basic chemical knowledge the structures of the binary complexes were proposed as shown in Fig. 3. These structures indicate that maleic acid acts as bidentate ligand depending upon the pH conditions. Oc-

tahedral structures are proposed to the complexes of all the metal ions. The VSEPR theory suggests that Pb^{II} and Cd^{II} complexes shall be octahedral because there are six outer electron pairs. This argument supports the structures of complexes proposed in Fig. 3.

Conclusions

- (i) The present biomimetic studies of metal ion complexes with maleic acid in acetonitrile-water mixtures indicate that all the complexes were protonated in acidic pH values.
- (ii) The predominant species detected were ML₂, ML₂H and ML₃.
- (iii) The log β values linearly vary with reciprocal of dielectric constant values of the medium, indicating the dominance of electrostatic forces over non-electrostatic forces.
- (iv) The order of the compounds influencing the magnitudes of the stability constants due to the incorporation of errors was alkali > acid > ligand > metal.
- (v) The higher concentration of free metal in low pH

values make the metal more bioavailable, more so in the case of toxic metals. At higher pH values, the higher concentrations of complex chemical species indicate that the metals are more amenable for transportation at higher pH values.

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